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ELECTRO-MECHANICAL TESTING OF SILVER CONDUCTIVE TEXTILES FOR STRAIN SENSING APPLICATIONS

Abstract: Strain sensors that are flexible and stretchable have become increasingly important for measuring various movements and forces and are now being used more frequently in smart textiles. They can be utilized to monitor movements of arms, legs, or individual joints, and have a high sensitivity for detecting large movements. However, there are only a few that are able to measure small movements. In this study, three different stretchable and flexible conductive textiles were tested electromechanically for their application as strain sensors. The conductive textiles exhibited the maximum change in resistance at 0.6N, with an observed sensitivity of 6.97 N^{-1} at a very small applied force of 0.1 N. These interesting finding exhibited the potential of conductive textiles as the promising wearable strain sensors to carry out important health measurements, such as breathing, bending, heartbeat, and vibrations.

Keywords: conductive textile, strain sensor, low strain

1. INTRODUCTION

The demand for soft electronics has led to the development of smart textiles, which are getting popular day by day. Traditional strain sensors such as metal foil or semiconductor-based sensors are bulky and rigid, which makes them unsuitable for wearable applications. One of the most notable types of smart sensors is the wearable, skin-mountable, and stretchable strain sensor. The sensor has numerous applications in fields like personalized health monitoring [1], human motion detection [2], and soft robotics or human-machine interfaces [3]. Smart textiles have the advantage of being able to interact naturally with the human body, which enables long-term monitoring. The sensors operate through capacitive or resistive means and are designed to convert physical deformation into electrical signals [4]. Resistive sensors are simple and suitable for a wide range of applications, as they detect changes in electrical resistance resulting from physical deformation. Conductive materials are necessary for both capacitive and resistive sensors, but conventional textile materials are typically insulators, so conductive materials must be added externally. This can be achieved through the integration of conductive materials [5] into the polymer matrix. Although numerous strain sensors with a large strain range and high sensitivity have been reported, there is relatively little documentation on sensors with high sensitivity at small strain ranges (< 5%). Textile strain sensors have become increasingly popular for detecting motion and measuring strain levels across a wide range.

Despite significant progress in the area, it remains a challenge to produce flexible and textile-based strain sensors with sensitivity to slight variations in load. This is why there is a growing need to develop textile strain sensors that are easy to manufacture and have exceptional sensitivity to small loads. These sensors can provide valuable information about an individual's health status, such as heartbeat, vibrations, torsions, or bending.

Our study proposes conductive clothes as strain-sensing material that holds promise for overcoming this challenge. These are silver-coated conductive clothes. The conductive clothes provide the benefits of both components, including the high electrical conductivity and flexibility of silver by using these conductive clothes, we can create highly sensitive, easy-to-manufactured textile-based sensors that can detect the smallest strains. The functionality of resistive strain sensors is based on the equation (1) [4].

$$R = \rho \frac{L}{A} \quad (1)$$

The electrical resistance (R) is determined by multiplying the material's specific electrical resistance (ρ) with the quotient of the distance between the measuring electrodes (L) and the cross-sectional area of the sample (A). For a change in electrical resistance to occur, the sensor load needs to alter either the geometry (L/A) or the specific electrical resistance of the material

(ρ). The operational mechanism of resistive strain sensors is a complex process that is influenced by multiple factors, including the textile structure, manufacturing process, and components utilized. These factors can significantly impact the sensor's accuracy and performance, emphasizing the need for careful consideration of these aspects to ensure optimal sensor performance.

In the present research, we have tested silver-based conductive textiles for strain sensing by choosing the textiles of different knitting styles. The sensitivity and resistive response of the textiles were investigated to examine their potential use as a strain sensor in the wearable health monitoring applications.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Three silver conductive fabrics namely Technik-tex P130 + B, Silitex, and Technik-tex P130 + B were purchased from Sheildex and labelled as C1, C2, and C3 respectively. All fabrics are knitted in warp and weft direction. The composition, electrical properties and knitting of these conductive textiles are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition and electrical properties of conductive textiles

Sample	Composition	R (Ω/m^2)	Knitting
C1	A hybrid knitted fabric consisting of (78% polyamide and 22% elastane).	2	warp and weft
C2	Silver metallized knitted fabric(78% polyamide and 22% elastane).	2	warp and weft
C3	Knitted fabric metalized with pure silver consists of 94% polyamide and 6% Dorlastan.	2	warp

The morphology of conductive clothes was performed by 3D Optical Profilometer (Huvitz BioImager® HRM-300) with Huvitz microscope. The associated Panasis software was used to analyze the surface of textile samples.

The electromechanical measurement of the conductive clothes was performed using a tensile

testing machine (Instron 34SC-2, city of Norwood, Massachusetts, USA) and the output is recorded as DC resistance (R_{dc}) by impedance analyzer (Hioki IM3590, Nagano, Japan). The textile samples were prepared by cutting the conductive clothes in size of 12 cm x 1 cm (W x L). During the measurement, these samples were fixed between the clamp of the machine. The testing set-up is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Conductive textile is fixed between the clamps of the tensile testing machine, both ends of the textiles are also connected with the HIOKI impedance analyzer to record the resistance change due to tensile force

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 2 represents the 2D profilometry images of the conductive textiles. Fig. 2(a)-2(c) show the photographs of different textiles. Fig. 2(d)-(f) displays the knitting styles of different textile samples. The knitting direction of the textile can be seen in the images. Sample C1 and C2 showed the knitting in the horizontal and vertical directions. The yarns were found to be looped

horizontally showing a weft knit whereas the parallel yarns were observed to be looped vertically at the same time, indicating warp knit. The wrap and weft knitting makes the textile stretchy in both directions. The conductive textile C3 was found to be knitted only in warp and stretchable in the vertical direction only. We also

observed the change in the knitting after stretching the textile. The small gaps in samples C2 and C3 were observed as highlighted by the marked area in Fig. 2(g), Fig. 2(h) whereas a few broken yarns are observed in Fig. 2 (i).

Fig. 2. a),b),c) photographs of conductive textiles d),e),f) 2D optical profiler images of the conductive textiles before applying tensile force g),h),i) 2D optical profiler images of the conductive textiles after applying tensile force

Fig. 3 represents the change in resistance of conductive clothes with applied strain at the rate of 0.05 N/s.

The maximum force of 1N is applied with a step size of 0.1 N.

Fig. 3. The resistive response of the conductive clothes a) relative change in resistance of conductive clothes and b) sensitivity of the conductive clothes with respect to applied force

From Fig. 3(a), it was observed that the resistance of conductive clothes increased with the applied forces. For the three conductive clothes, the maximum resistive response was observed at the applied force of 0.6 N. In the case of samples C1 and C3, the change in resistance was observed until an applied force of 0.4 N. After 0.4 N, the applied force showed a negligible effect on the resistance change whereas sample C2 showed a slight change in resistance after 0.4 N.

Fig. 3(b) represents the sensitivity of samples C1, C2 and C3. The sensor's sensitivity was calculated using equation (2)

$$S = \frac{\Delta R/R_0}{\Delta F} \quad (1)$$

The sensitivity of the samples was found to be decreased in sensitivity with an increase in applied force. The sensitivity of sample C1 was obtained higher than the other two conductive textiles. The sensitivity of samples C1, C2 and C3 were 6.97 N^{-1} , 5.35 N^{-1} and 2.95 N^{-1} respectively at 0.1 N force.

4. CONCLUSION

In this work, silver-based textiles were tested as strain sensors. These textiles showed a promising response in the form of resistance variations even at a small value of applied force. This work demonstrates the potential use of conductive textiles as strain sensors capable of detecting smaller movements such as breathing, bending, heartbeat, and vibrations.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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